

Inhibition of fibrillation of lysozyme by folic acid functionalized cerium oxide nanoparticle

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Effect of folic acid functionalized nanoceria on fibrillation of lysozyme has been studied using spectroscopic and microscopic tools. Both bare and functionalized CeONP are capable to retard fibrillation of lysozyme. Also interaction of lysozyme with nanoceria has been studied employing multiple biophysical techniques. The intrinsic fluorescence of lysozyme is quenched in presence of nanoceria. Adsorption of lysozyme causes significant reduction on fibrillization of lysozyme. Mechanism of quenching has been interpreted.

Keywords: Fibrillation, lysozyme, cerium oxide, nanoparticle.

Introduction

Nanoceria or cerium oxide nanoparticle has become a growing field in medical applications, cosmetic products, polishing materials according to their specific, catalytic, light properties¹⁻³. Indeed, when nanoparticles enter a biological fluid, they undergo surface modification due to dynamic interactions with biological components, especially protein adsorption⁴. An adsorbed layer on protein called 'protein corona' is formed. 'Hard corona' is composed of proteins with strong binding affinity to the surface of nanoparticle. The soft corona, on the other hand, is composed of weakly bound proteins. The protein-NP complexes interact immediately with living systems and affect the biological response *in vitro* experiments⁵. In this work we have studied adsorption of lysozyme on nanoceria.

Deposition of amyloid fibril (aggregation or misfolding of proteins) of protein in different organ is a pathological hallmark of various degenerative disease such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson, Prion, type II diabetes etc.⁶⁻¹⁰. Recently nanotechnology is at the centre of interest to tackle with those disorders. The present work portrays a strategy to inhibit fibrillation of egg hen white lysozyme (Lyz), which is structurally homologous to human Lyz and responsible for systematic amyloidosis disorder¹¹. Cerium oxide, one of the important rare earth oxide due to its versatile application in bio-

medical field¹², is still seeking scope for inhibition of amyloid related disorder. In this article, first we have synthesized spherical shaped cerium oxide nanoparticle (CeONP) hydrothermally and functionalized it with folic acid (FA). Then effect of functionalized CeONP has been investigated on fibrillation of Lyz. The amyloid growth is monitored by Thioflavin T (ThT), circular dichroism, and fluorescence microscopy study.

Experimental

Materials:

Hen egg white lysozyme was purchased from Sisco Research Laboratory, cerium nitrate hexahydrate ((Ce(NO₃)₂·6H₂O)), trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO), hexadecylamine (HDA), (3-aminopropyl)trimethoxysilane (APTMS), folic acid (FA), N-hydroxysulfosuccinimide (NHS), 1-ethyl-3-[3-dimethylaminopropyl] carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) were acquired from Sigma Aldrich. All experiments were performed in 10 mM citrate-phosphate buffer (pH 7.0).

Synthesis of cerium oxide nanoparticle (CeONP):

Synthesis of CeONP was carried out following our previous protocol¹³. Briefly, in a 100 mL teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave containing 5 mL 0.02 (M) cerium(III) nitrate aqueous solution, 20 mL cyclohexane was added, followed by

subsequent addition of 0.02 (M) trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO) and 0.04 (M) hexadecylamine (HDA). The mixture was subjected to a magnetic stirrer for 30 min until a clear solution is obtained. Then the sealed autoclave was transferred to an oven at 180°C for 6 h and cooled at room temperature spontaneously. The solution was centrifuged to separate the precipitate and washed by ethanol-water repeatedly. The solid was dried in vacuum desiccator overnight. The as obtained cerium hydroxide (Ce(OH)₃) was calcined at 800°C for 6 h to get cerium oxide nanoparticles (CeO₂NP).

Synthesis of folic acid (FA) functionalized CeONP:

Functionalization of folic acid on CeONP was carried out following Hijaz *et al.*¹⁴. Briefly, at first thin layer of APTMS was coated on CeONP for amine (-NH₂) functionalization by mixing CeONP aqueous suspension with APTMS. This amine functionalization facilitates folic acid to conjugate on the surface of CeONP. This conjugation takes place using the coupling reaction of 1-ethyl-3-[3-dimethylaminopropyl] carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) and N-hydroxysulfosuccinimide. A solution of FA, NH₂ functionalized CeONP, EDC and NHS in 1:1:2.2:11.2 molar ratio was stirred in a magnetic stirrer for 24 h at room temperature. The precipitate was centrifuged and washed several times by water and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) to remove excess EDC, NHS and unreacted FA. The as obtained product was dried in vacuum desiccator overnight to get FA functionalized CeONP (FA-CeONP).

Characterization of CeONP and FA-CeONP:

The crystalline nature of as synthesized NPs were assessed by X-ray diffraction patterns (XRD; D-8 Advanced, Bruker) collected at intervals of 0.02° (2θ). FT-IR spectra were obtained on a RX-1 Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer with samples prepared as KBr pellets. HRTEM images were obtained with a JEOL-JEM-2100 transmission electron microscope at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV.

Steady state fluorescence spectroscopy:

The steady state fluorescence spectra was measured using Shimadzu spectrofluorimeter (model RF 5301) by exciting the protein at 280 nm and the emission spectra were recorded at 290–500 nm. Slits were adjusted to 5 nm for both excitation and emission spectra.

Preparation of fibrillar solutions:

Lysozyme (Lyz) solution (10 mg/mL) were dissolved in glycine-HCl buffer (pH 2.2) containing 100 mM NaCl and 2 mM NaN₃. 2 mL of this solution was added to 18 mL by 20 mM glycine-HCl buffer (pH 2.2). The solution was stirred at 60°C and aliquots were collected from the solution at regular time interval. Lyz fibril formation was monitored by ThT assay.

Thioflavin T (ThT) fluorescence spectroscopy:

Fluorescence intensity of ThT increases while binding amyloid. Thus ThT dye was used to quantify amyloid formation of Lyz. ThT was added to Lyz samples (10 μM) to a final concentration of 20 μM in buffer and incubated at 37°C for 1 h. The fluorescence spectra were measured using Shimadzu spectrofluorimeter (model RF 5301) by exciting the dye at 440 nm and the emission spectra were recorded at 485 nm. Slits were adjusted to 3 nm for both excitation and emission spectra.

Circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy:

CD spectra of the amyloid samples were measured by Jasco spectropolarimeter (J-815), using a rectangular quartz cuvette of path length 1 cm. Far UV-CD spectra were collected with protein concentration 7 μM within range 190–260 nm.

ThT staining and fluorescence microscopy:

10 μL of each Lyz alone and Lyz incubated in presence of CeONP and FA-CeONP were mixed with ThT dye for 1 h. Then the samples were dropped on a freshly cleaned glass slides covered with coverslips. Fluorescence microscopy images were carried out with Leica DMI8 with UV laser as excitation source. The filter used for ThT excitation and emission was cube DAPI.

Results and discussion

Characterization of CeONP and FA-CeONP:

Particle size and phase of synthesized CeONP were analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). The XRD peaks (Fig. 1a) of CeONP correspond to face centered cubic CeO₂ (JCPDS no. 81-0792). The particle size measured from TEM particle size distribu-

tion (Fig. 1) analysis is 18.9 ± 1.5 nm. The interplaner distance obtained from high resolution TEM is 0.31 nm which corresponds to (111) plane of CeONP (Fig. 1).

Fluorescence quenching:

Fluorescence spectroscopy is an important tool to study the conformational change of protein when adsorbed on nanoparticle as it is highly sensitive to change in fluorescence property of protein which originates from tryptophan and tyrosine residue. Tryptophan is extremely sensitive to its microenvironment. The effect of CeONP on the fluorescence intensity of Lyz has been illustrated in Fig. 2a.

The above quenching is quantitatively estimated using Stern-Volmer equation

$$F_0/F = 1 + K_{SV}[Q]$$

where, F_0 and F are the steady state fluorescence emission intensities in the absence and presence of the quencher respectively. K_{SV} is the Stern-Volmer quenching constant and

$[Q]$ is the concentration of CeONP. The Stern-Volmer plot has been displayed in Fig. 2b. The K_{SV} value for quenching is $2.1 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$. Another study to confirm the quenching mechanism is time resolved fluorescence measurement, which is a sensitive tool for tracking local environment changes of fluorophore. The fluorescence lifetime of Lyz doesn't change with successive addition of CeONP suggesting static quenching.

ThT fluorescence assay:

At first formation of amyloid aggregate was monitored by ThT fluorescence assay, since binding of ThT dye with amyloid causes significant increase in fluorescence intensity of ThT¹⁵. Native Lyz incubated in 20 mM glycine HCl buffer (pH 2.2) at 60°C for 10 h produced amyloid fibrils of Lyz. During fibrillization ThT fluorescence intensity at 485 nm changes in sigmoidal manner (Fig. 3) with respect to time. It is evident that increase in fluorescence intensity of ThT gets reduced in presence of CeONP and again by FA-CeONP (concentration 16 μM).

Fig. 1. (a) XRD of CeONP, TEM particle size distribution of (b) CeONP, (c) FA-CeONP and (d) HRTEM of CeONP.

Fig. 2. (a) Quenching of fluorescence of Lyz with increasing concentration of CeONP and (b) corresponding Stern-Volmer plot.

Fig. 3. Change in fluorescence intensity of ThT at 485 nm with respect to time in absence of CeONP (black line), CeONP (brown line) and FA-CeONP (pink line).

Circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy study:

Apart from above spectroscopic investigation we have studied effect of CeONP and FA-CeONP on the structural change of native Lyz upon amyloid growth by Circular Dichroism (CD) spectroscopy. The far UV-CD spectra depicts that native Lyz possess (7 μ M) two negative minimum at 208 nm and 222 nm (Fig. 4, curve 1), which correspond to π to π^* transition and n to π^* transition of α -helix respectively¹⁶. Fibrillation of native Lyz in presence of CeONP and FA-CeONP shows that magnitude of CD spectra of Lyz is reduced and this reduction is concentration dependent (curve 2-6). This suggests reduction in α -helical content of Lyz during fibrillation, in other words CeONPs shield native Lyz from secondary structural change on fibrillation.

ThT staining and fluorescence microscopy:

To support the above findings fluorescence imaging of

Fig. 4. Far UV-CD spectral analysis of Lyz solution during fibril formation in presence of increasing concentration of (a) CeONP and (b) FA-CeONP.

various amyloid samples were performed with and without addition of bare and FA functionalized CeONP. Fig. 5 displays fluorescence microscopy images of Lyz solutions containing various NP. Undoubtedly density of fibrills are diminished in presence of CeONP as well as FA-CeONP.

Fig. 5. Fluorescence microscopy images of Lyz solution in (a) absence and presence of (b) CeONP and (c) FA-CeONP stained by ThT dye.

Conclusion

In summary we have studied adsorption of Lyz on CeONP from spectroscopic viewpoint. Also we have performed effect of CeONP and FA-CeONP on amyloid growth of Lyz which has been verified by spectroscopy and microscopy protocol. Results show that inhibitory efficiency of FA-CeONP is greater than CeONP.

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